

The impact of the pandemic and school closures on non-cognitive characteristics: Evidence from PISA

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Summary

1. This study investigates the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on students' non-cognitive skills using data from the OECD's PISA surveys (2012–2022).
 2. It focuses on three key indicators: sense of belonging to school, growth mindset, and experiences of bullying across five industrialized regions.
 3. Findings reveal a short-term decline and partial long-term recovery in students' sense of belonging, alongside a consistent drop in growth mindset and a reduction in frequent bullying.
 4. Girls, migrant students, and those from lower socioeconomic backgrounds were disproportionately affected.
 5. The study underscores the need for targeted policy interventions to support student well-being and resilience in the post-pandemic period.
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1. Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic disrupted education for more than 1.5 billion children and youth globally, with school closures profoundly affecting student learning. While cognitive learning losses have been extensively studied, less is known about the pandemic's impact on non-cognitive outcomes such as students' sense of belonging, growth mindset, and exposure to bullying. These dimensions are vital as non-cognitive skills play a critical role in students' academic success and well-being, especially during crises.

In Quintero-Peña, Volante and De Witte (2025) we address this gap by examining how the pandemic influenced non-cognitive characteristics using data from the OECD's Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA). The study analyzes trends between 2012 and 2022 across five industrialized regions: Canada, the United States, Australia, New Zealand, and Europe. These countries offer a comprehensive cross-section of Western education systems and experienced varying degrees of school closures. The focus on sense of belonging, mindset, and bullying provides insight into how students adapted socially and emotionally to the prolonged interruption of in-person education.

2. Data and Methodology

The study utilizes PISA data, focusing on five regions—Canada, the United States, Australia, New Zealand, and Europe—over the period 2012 to 2022. The analysis includes responses from 980,403 students, with robust student-level weights ensuring national representativeness. Three non-cognitive variables are examined: sense of belonging to school, growth mindset, and frequent

exposure to bullying. *Sense of belonging* is measured using Item Response Theory (IRT) based on six items related to inclusion, friendship, and connectedness at school. *Growth mindset* is derived from students' level of agreement with the statement "Your intelligence is something about you that you can't change much," with lower values indicating a stronger growth mindset. *Frequent bullying* is based on an OECD index capturing students' reported experiences of bullying over the past 12 months. These variables were consistently measured in recent PISA rounds, enabling longitudinal comparisons.

To estimate the impact of the pandemic, the study applies ordinary least squares (OLS) regression models with controls for gender, migrant status, and socioeconomic background. Country-level variables, such as school closure duration and changes in education spending, are also included. Additionally, teacher shortages and excess mortality data are incorporated to capture broader contextual influences. Country fixed effects and time trends are used to account for pre-existing differences and isolate the pandemic's impact on non-cognitive outcomes.

3. Results

The study identifies significant effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on students' non-cognitive characteristics. Starting with the sense of belonging to school, a nuanced pattern emerges. In the short term, students experienced a decline of 0.04 standard deviations (SD) in their sense of belonging between 2018 and 2022. However, the longer-term trend shows a recovery of 0.049 SD, particularly in Canada and the United States. Despite this recovery, there were still substantial losses in countries such as the USA

and New Zealand, where the decrease reached 0.12 SD.

Socioeconomic status (ESCS), gender, and migrant status were significant predictors. Girls reported lower levels of school belonging than boys, and migrant students showed a significant negative association. Teacher shortages and high excess mortality also correlated with a reduced sense of belonging, underlining the broader impacts of systemic and contextual stressors during the pandemic. The second key result pertains to growth mindset. The pandemic was associated with a statistically significant decline of 0.08 SD in growth mindset across the studied regions. This decline was most pronounced in New Zealand, Canada, and Europe, where students increasingly adopted a fixed view of intelligence. In contrast, the United States showed relatively smaller changes. Interestingly, students from more affluent backgrounds (higher ESCS) reported greater losses in growth mindset, while girls and migrant students displayed a stronger growth mindset overall. Longer school closures and teacher shortages also negatively influenced this outcome, suggesting that both educational disruptions and reduced support structures played a role in shifting students' beliefs about their own potential.

In terms of bullying, the data reveal a 5% decrease in the likelihood of students reporting frequent bullying between 2018 and 2022. This reduction was consistent across all countries and both genders. It appears that school closures and the shift to remote learning limited opportunities for in-person bullying, and even cyberbullying did not fully replace this behaviour. However, the decrease was not evenly distributed. Migrant students continued to experience higher rates of bullying, while girls and students from higher socioeconomic backgrounds reported lower rates.

Further analysis shows that students from lower socioeconomic backgrounds experienced more significant declines in the sense of belonging, but less so in growth mindset, possibly reflecting adaptive non-cognitive strategies in disadvantaged contexts. The study also finds that the longer the schools remained fully closed, the greater the losses in the sense of belonging, though this also corresponded to a small recovery in growth mindset. Finally, teacher shortages emerged as a consistent negative factor across all three non-cognitive domains.

Overall, the findings suggest that the pandemic's effects on students' social and emotional development were complex and heterogeneous. While some indicators show signs of recovery, others, such as mindset and bullying disparities, reveal lasting consequences that disproportionately affect already vulnerable groups, including girls, migrants, and students from lower socioeconomic backgrounds. These results underscore the need for targeted support and long-term monitoring of student well-being in the post-pandemic period.

4. Policy Recommendations

The findings from this study point to several policy directions to support students' non-cognitive development in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic. As schools worldwide seek to recover from the disruptions caused by school closures, targeted and inclusive policies are essential to mitigate the long-term consequences for students' well-being and educational trajectories.

First, education systems must pay sufficient attention to the emotional and psychological well-being of students. The observed decline in the sense of belonging and the shift toward a fixed mindset highlight the importance of

fostering supportive and inclusive school environments. Interventions aimed at rebuilding a sense of school connectedness, such as mentorship programs, social-emotional learning curricula, and peer support networks, should be scaled up, especially for girls, migrant students, and those from lower socioeconomic backgrounds who were disproportionately affected.

Second, addressing structural weaknesses exposed by the pandemic is crucial. Teacher shortages significantly undermined students' sense of belonging and mindset. Investments in teacher recruitment, retention, and professional development are therefore essential. In particular, training programs should include components on fostering resilience and growth mindset in students, equipping educators with tools to address both academic and emotional needs in the classroom.

Third, the reduction in bullying suggests that changes in school environments during closures had some positive effects. Policymakers should build on these insights to develop anti-bullying strategies that go beyond traditional in-person settings and extend to online and hybrid learning contexts. Sustained efforts to create safe school climates are essential to protect vulnerable groups from relational, verbal, and physical victimization.

For the European Commission, these findings highlight the urgent need to integrate non-cognitive skills into the broader framework of educational recovery and resilience. As the EU continues to implement initiatives like the "Pathways to School Success," greater emphasis should be placed on monitoring and improving students' emotional well-being, particularly in light of the pandemic's lasting impact. The Commission can support Member States by funding targeted programs

that promote a sense of belonging and growth mindset, especially among vulnerable groups such as migrants and economically disadvantaged students. Additionally, EU-wide data collection on non-cognitive outcomes through instruments like PISA should be encouraged and expanded, enabling cross-country comparisons and fostering policy learning across education systems.

Finally, the data demonstrate the need for a more comprehensive monitoring system for non-cognitive outcomes in education. Including indicators such as school belonging, mindset, and bullying in national and international assessments can help policymakers track recovery and design evidence-based interventions. Integrating these dimensions into the broader education policy agenda will ensure that learning recovery encompasses not only academic skills but also the emotional and social competencies that are critical for lifelong success.

References

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